

Assessment of Different Cutaneous Granulomatous Lesions: Etiological, Clinical and Histopathological Study

Sreelatha Kurapati¹, Keerthi Gourishetty², S Naresh Babu³, B. Swapna Kumari⁴

¹Associate Professor, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar

²Assistant Professor, Fr. Columbo Institute of Medical Sciences, Warangal

³Associate Professor, Prathima Relief Institute of Medical Sciences, Warangal

⁴Government Medical College, Mulugu

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Corresponding Author: Dr. S Naresh Babu

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Abstract:

Background: Cutaneous granulomatous lesions encompass a wide range of dermatological conditions with diverse etiologies, including infections, foreign bodies, and systemic diseases. Accurate diagnosis is critical for effective management, necessitating a thorough understanding of their clinical presentation and histopathological features.

Aim and Objectives: To evaluate the frequency and patterns of different cutaneous granulomatous lesions with its clinico-histopathological correlation to reach etiological diagnosis.

Materials and Method: This study was descriptive, observational study aimed at assessing the etiological, clinical, and histopathological characteristics of different cutaneous granulomatous lesions. The study was conducted at Department of Pathology, for duration of one year. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) before the commencement of the study and after meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Results: Majority of the patients were from the age group of 10-20 years. male to female ration was 2.43 : 1. Skin and Subcutaneous were major was major site of granuloma, most common Etiology among study population was due to tuberculosis.

Conclusion: This study highlights the diverse etiological spectrum and clinical presentations of cutaneous granulomatous lesions. Histopathological examination remains indispensable for accurate diagnosis, providing essential insights into the underlying causes.

Keywords: Cutaneous granulomatous lesions, Etiology, Clinical characteristics, Histopathology, Diagnostic accuracy, Infectious granulomas, Non-infectious granulomas, Systemic diseases, Dermatology, Granulomatous inflammation.

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Introduction

Cutaneous granulomatous lesions are a diverse group of dermatological conditions characterized by the formation of granulomas, which are organized clusters of macrophages transformed into epithelioid cells, often surrounded by lymphocytes. These lesions arise in response to a variety of stimuli, including infectious agents, foreign materials, and autoimmune processes. Given their broad etiological spectrum and often overlapping clinical presentations, a detailed clinico-histopathological and etiological assessment is crucial for accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

Granulomatous inflammation is a specific type of chronic inflammation that occurs when the immune system attempts to contain substances perceived as foreign but is unable to eliminate. This response leads to the formation of granulomas, which can be

seen in conditions like tuberculosis, leprosy, sarcoidosis, and foreign body reactions. These granulomas typically consist of macrophages that have transformed into epithelioid cells and multinucleated giant cells, surrounded by a collar of lymphocytes. The clinical manifestations of cutaneous granulomatous lesions vary widely, presenting as papules, nodules, plaques, or ulcers, depending on the underlying cause and the host's immune response.

Histopathological examination plays a pivotal role in diagnosing granulomatous lesions. The presence and characteristics of granulomas, such as caseation necrosis, the type of inflammatory cells, and the identification of causative organisms or foreign materials, provide critical diagnostic information. Special stains and techniques, like Ziehl-Neelsen for mycobacteria and Grocott's

methenamine silver for fungi, are often employed to identify specific pathogens. The histological appearance of granulomas can also help distinguish between infectious and non-infectious causes.

The etiological spectrum of cutaneous granulomatous lesions is extensive. Infectious causes include bacterial infections like tuberculosis and leprosy, fungal infections such as histoplasmosis and sporotrichosis, and parasitic infestations like leishmaniasis. Non-infectious causes encompass sarcoidosis, foreign body reactions, and autoimmune diseases such as granulomatosis with polyangiitis. Each of these conditions presents unique diagnostic and therapeutic challenges, necessitating a comprehensive approach to patient evaluation.

A thorough diagnostic approach integrates clinical, histopathological, and microbiological data. Detailed clinical history and physical examination are fundamental to identifying potential etiological factors, including travel history, occupational exposures, and systemic diseases. Histopathological examination remains the cornerstone of diagnosis, providing essential insights into the nature of the granulomas and their associated features. Microbiological cultures, serological tests, and molecular diagnostics are often necessary to confirm the specific etiology.

Thus this study aimed to evaluate the frequency and patterns of different cutaneous granulomatous lesions with its clinico-histopathological correlation to reach etiological diagnosis.

Materials and Method

This study was descriptive, observational study aimed at assessing the etiological, clinical, and histopathological characteristics of different cutaneous granulomatous lesions. The study was conducted at Department of Pathology, for duration of one year. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) before the commencement of the study and after meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria given below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all ages presenting with cutaneous granulomatous lesions.
- Patients willing to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who have received treatment for their granulomatous lesions prior to the study.

- Patients unwilling or unable to provide informed consent.

Method

Clinical Evaluation

1. **Patient History:** Detailed patient history was obtained, including demographic data (age, sex, occupation), history of travel, exposure to potential infectious agents, systemic symptoms, and previous medical history.
2. **Physical Examination:** A thorough dermatological examination was conducted to document the clinical characteristics of the lesions, including their size, shape, number, distribution, and any associated systemic findings.

Histopathological Examination

1. **Biopsy Procedure:** Skin biopsies was performed on representative lesions. Standard punch or excisional biopsy techniques was used depending on the size and location of the lesions.
2. **Sample Processing:** Biopsy samples were fixed in 10% formalin, processed, and embedded in paraffin. Sections were stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) for routine histopathological examination.
3. **Special Stains and Techniques:**
 - Ziehl-Neelsen stain for acid-fast bacilli (e.g., *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*).
 - Grocott's methenamine silver (GMS) stain for fungal elements.
 - Periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) stain for fungi and certain parasites.
 - Polarized light microscopy for identification of foreign bodies.

Statistical Analysis

Collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel 2016 for further statistical analysis. Categorical data were expressed in terms of frequency and percentages and quantitative data were expressed in terms of mean and standard deviation. SPSS version of 25 were used for statistical analysis

Observation and Results

In the study we have included total 55 patients with skin biopsies after histopathological confirmation of granulomatous lesions and their outcomes are as given below

Table 1 : Age and Gender distribution among study population

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
< 10 Years	4	7.3
10 -20 Years	17	30.9
21 - 30 Years	11	20
31 - 40 Years	12	21.8
41 - 50 Years	3	5.5
> 50 Years	7	12.7
Gender		
Male	39	70.9
Female	16	29.1

Majority of the patients were from the age group of 10-20 years followed by 31-40 years, 21-30 years, > 50 years and other age groups, also we have observed that, majority of the patients were male compared females and male to female ration was 2.43 : 1

Figure 1 : Distribution of site of granuloma among study population**Table 2 : Etiological distribution of granuloma among study population**

Etiology	Frequency	Percentage
Leprosy	12	21.8
Tuberculosis	20	36.4
Fungal	8	14.5
Foreign Body	5	9.1
Unknown	10	18.2

We have observed most common Etiology among study population was due to tuberculosis, followed by leprosy, unknow Etiology, due to fungal and foreign body as shown in above table.

Discussion

Cutaneous granulomas are frequently seen in dermatology clinics and present a significant diagnostic challenge for dermatologists. While a skin biopsy can confirm a granulomatous reaction and often suggest a diagnosis, histological analysis alone is sometimes inadequate, necessitating additional tests to reach a definitive diagnosis. The formation of granulomas is due to a type IV

hypersensitivity reaction triggered by infectious and non-infectious antigens. In North India, granulomatous dermatoses are common and often have overlapping clinical presentations, making it crucial to identify the exact etiology for appropriate treatment. [1]

In the present study we have observed that, Majority of the patients were from the age group of 10-20 years followed by 31-40 years, 21-30 years, > 50 years and other age groups, also we have observed that, majority of the patients were male compared females and male to female ration was 2.43 : 1, in the study by Harish S. Permi et al [2] observed that, Majority of patients were seen in the

age group of 21-30 years in 65 (23.64%) cases. Males were affected predominantly in 144 (52.36%) cases and females in 131 (47.64%) cases. Male to female ratio was 1.09:1. Our observation also supported by Kumari et al. other study by Gautam *et al.*, [3] in finding of predominance of male in granulomatous skin lesion showing male (60.84%), female (39.16%) with M:F ratio of 1.5:1.

In the present study most common site of granuloma was skin and subcutaneous, followed by lymph node, bones and joints and other site as shown above table. Supported to our study by Harish S. Permi et al also observed The commonest site was skin and subcutaneous tissues followed by lymph nodes, bones and joints, respiratory system, gastrointestinal tract, breast female reproductive system, urinary tract, male reproductive system, gall bladder and brain. Commonest site of the skin lesions was upper extremity which is comparable with the study done by Gautam et al but not with Zafar et al in which most lesion were found in head and neck region. [4]

In our study, most common Etiology among study population was due to tuberculosis, followed by leprosy, unknow Etiology, due to fungal and foreign body. Study by Bal et al [5] observed infectious granulomatous dermatoses were most common Etiology in their study supporting our study. Leprosy remained the significant causative reason for infectious granulomatous dermatoses succeeded by tuberculosis of skin. Another study by Qureshi et al [6] concluded cutaneous leishmaniasis 56.7% as the leading cause of granulomatous dermatoses

Study by Mirza M et al. [7] The commonest fungal infection was aspergillosis followed by rhinosporidiosis and chromoblastomycosis. In the present study we have observed fungal granuloma among 8 patients. Different studies reported fungal cutaneous granuloma in range of 2.7% to 3.3% [8-10]. Bal et al and Potekar et al concluded leprosy as a leading cause of cutaneous granulomatous disease. [11] in our study it was second most commonest cause.

Conclusion

Based on our observations, we conclude that the etiology of granulomatous dermatoses significantly varies by geographic region. Granulomatous inflammation is more prevalent in males, with tuberculosis being the most common cause, followed by leprosy. Clinically, these skin lesions often have overlapping presentations.

Histopathology, in conjunction with a thorough history and relevant clinical examination, is crucial for diagnosing and sub-classifying cutaneous granulomatous lesions. Our study highlights various important chronic granulomatous inflammatory dermatoses in this region, which will be beneficial for management and the implementation of health programs.

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